

“STUDY ON MARKETING OF FUNGICIDE (SAAF) FOR SUGARCANE CROP IN BIJNOR DISTRICT OF UTTAR PRADESH”**1 Prateek Kumar Monish¹, 2 Dr. Ameesh John Stephen²**

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ameesh.stephen@shiats.edu.in**Abstract:**

The Present study was conducted in the year 2022-2023 with a sample of 120 Sugarcane farmers in district of Bijnor of Uttar Pradesh State. The study reveals that the quantity sales of Fungicide of UPL Ltd in Bijnor district was found to be total of 930 kg. The market share and key existing competitors of SAAF Fungicide was found to be Bayer (Netivo), Syngenta (Taspa), Tata Rallis (Blitox). The maximum share of Fungicide in the district was UPL (SAAF) a total market share of 32.30%. There were 2 market channels found in the district for fungicides.

Keywords: Market Share, Market Channel, Key-existing Competitors.

Introduction:

Agriculture is described as the backbone of Indian economy. Agriculture accounts for 22% of India's GDP, while agriculture employs around 58 percent of the population. The Indian economy relies heavily on village agricultural and modern agriculture. India is top in the world in milk production. Fruits, cashew nuts, coconuts, and tea are in second place, followed by wheat, sugar, and vegetables, and tobacco and rice. Despite having the world's second-largest fertile land area, India's agricultural output, particularly in wheat and rice, falls short of its enormous potential, with rapid population expansion and industrialization contributing to low agricultural productivity relative to potential. Sugarcane (*Saccharum officinarum*) family Gramineae (*Poaceae*) is widely grown crop in India. It provides employment to over a million people directly or indirectly besides contributing significantly to the national exchequer. Sugarcane growing countries of the world lay between the latitude 36.7° north and 31.0° south of the equator extending from tropical to subtropical zones. Sugar cane originated in New Guinea where it has been known for thousands of years. Sugar cane plants spread along human migration routes to Asia and the Indian subcontinent. Here it cross-bred with some wild sugar cane relatives to produce the commercial sugar cane we know today. Agricultural chemicals are essential for our survival and the health of our families and pets. Pesticides will

remain a primary weapon in our continual war against pests until and until better, more efficient, and more cost-effective methods of pest control are developed. Growers in India should be informed of recent developments in this field. Agrochemical, often known as agrichemical, is a generic name for agricultural chemicals. Pesticides such as insecticides, herbicides, and fungicides are commonly referred to as agrochemicals. Synthetic fertilisers, hormones, and other chemical growth stimulants, as well as concentrated stocks of animal dung, are all included. Agrochemicals are often poisonous, therefore bulk storage must be tightly managed, or spilling of such chemicals could pose environmental or health risks.

Material and Method:**Selection of the District:**

Uttar Pradesh consists 75 districts out of that Bijnor district was selected purposively for the study and the researcher is well conversant with language, geography area, agriculture and other aspect of the area.

Selection of Block:

Bijnor consists 11 blocks out of that Nehtaur block was be purposively selected for present study.

Selection of Village:

A complete no. of village in Nehtaur block out of that 5% of village was be selected randomly for the study.

Name of District	Name of block	Name of villages	No. of respondents Selected
Bijnor	Nehtaur	Mahua	12
		Aaku	12
		Dhakoli	12
		Harpur	12
		Khijarpur	12
		Mukimpur	12
		Nijatpur	12
		Papsara	12
		Sedhi	12
		Mirjapur	12

Selection of Respondents:

Sugarcane growers of selected villages were be listed and 10% of farmers from each village was be randomly selected. The selections were done by using simple random sampling method for the purpose of the study.

Analytical Tools**Percentage Formula:**

The percentage formula is used to find the share of a whole in terms of 100. Using this formula, you can represent a number as a fraction of 100.

$$\text{Percentage} = (\text{Value}/\text{Total Value}) \times 100$$

$$\% \text{ increase} = [(\text{New number} - \text{Original number})/\text{Original number}] \times 100$$

Market Share Formula:

$$\text{Market share} = \frac{\text{Total sales of the company}}{\text{Total sales of the market}} \times 100$$

Result And Discussion

The result is a presentation of the findings of the given study, purely based on the objective:

To Analyse The Market Share For Variou Fungicides In The Study Area.

Table 1: Market share of different companies for fungicide sales in Bijnor district (2022-2023)

Sl.No.	Companyname	Brand name	Quantitiesale	Value (inlakh)	Market share (%)
1.	Bayer	Netivo (kg.)	1800	26.32	17.66
2.	UPL	Saaf (kg)	930	48.15	32.30
3.	Syngenta	Taspa (lit)	1190	36.15	24.25
4.	Tata rallies	Blitox(kg)	860	20.29	13.62
5.	Others		712	18.12	12.17
	Total		6952	149.03	100

The UPL Ltd company is in competition with both national and multinational companies like Bayer, Syngenta, BASF, Tata chemicals, Pesticide India, etc are some of the major competitors. These companies with early entry in business of Fungicide have large

customers base and were able to capture more market share. **Table 1** reveals that the highest market share was found to be of UPL (32.30) followed by Syngenta (24.25 percent), Bayer (17.66 percent), Tata Rallies (13.62 percent), and others (12.17 Percent).

Market Channel for various fungicides in study area

Channel I

Channel II

Conclusion

Agriculture is an substantial source of income for the majority of the country's population. Farmers are confronted with serious issues such as poor yield, pest disease, natural catastrophes, and so on; while natural calamities are beyond our control, insect and disease problems can be handled with the use of various pesticides, resulting in an increase in yield. The use of fungicides has been growing in recent years. The current study, "study on marketing of fungicide (saaf) for Sugarcane crop in bijnor district of uttar pradesh " was started with the specific goals of determining the socio-economic profile of the respondents, analysing the market share for various fungicides in the study area, and determining the market potential of fungicide SAAF. To identify the barriers to the marketing of the fungicide SAAF and to make policy recommendations. The information was gathered from 120 people, including 15 dealers, and analysed using a questionnaire. The study concluded that study area have four major players (company) in the field of fungicide market i.e., UPL, Syngenta, Bayer and Tata Rallies were functioning to supply fungicide. The highest market share was found of Saaf (UPL) (32.68%), market share followed by Taspa (Syngenta) (21.82%), Netivo (Bayer) (19.21%) and Blitox (Tata Rallies) (14.88%). There were found huge (98.12%) potential of fungicide in the study area, agriculture is major for source of income. Fungicides used by the respondents in the study area are UPL (44.17%), Syngenta (25.84%), Bayer (17.5%), Tata Rallies (10%) and Others (2.5%). The UPL Company has adopted promotional activities like Demonstration, magazines, boarding, tour and campaigning in the study area.

The study discovered that the fungicide SAAF is more effective against illness. Dealers provided information on the fungicide's market share and Market Potential. As a preventative step, several farmers have sprayed this fungicide. Retailer recommendations, brand popularity, price, and the timely availability of the fungicide SAAF are all factors that influence farmers' purchasing decisions. Fungi infestations are most common in food crops such as

SUGARCANE, paddy, potato, mango, and chilli. According to the report, the district of Bijnor has a greater demand for fungicide. SUGARCANE, paddy, chilli, and grapes are among the most common food crops farmed in Anantapur. Fungicide use is critical in such situations. The current study focuses on the market size of UPL Ltd's fungicide

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